

WORLD CULTURAL DIVERSITY IN IMPROVING MULTICULTURAL COMPETENCIES

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***Abstract:** The article is devoted to the role of world cultural diversity in the formation and improvement of multicultural competencies necessary for a modern person. It is stressed that language is not only a neutral tool for the communication of ideas, but it takes part in the production of thought.*

***Key words:** cultural diversity, analysis, connections, perception, reduction, opportunity, communication*

One of the most effective approaches in understanding the cultural diversity of the world, the formation and improvement of multicultural competencies necessary for a modern person, in our opinion, is a textual approach. With this approach, attention is paid to the relationship between language and culture. Various language constructions are the basis for broadcasting messages, thus forming a cultural field, relationships within the text and, of course, between culture and language. Everything that is fixed and reflected in the language will certainly remain in the culture. By understanding the language, one understands the culture. With this approach, structural analysis is carried out through all the variety of features and methods. The study of linguistic structures, the structure of the language, discursive practices, etc., allows you to establish deep connections, identify interdependencies in semiotic spheres and the multicultural space as a whole. "The ability to read cultural messages, to own cultural codes and passwords means the ability to be part of the cultural space, to be included in society. Culture itself acts as a special space of signs, isolated from the general social field" [4].

We share the faith of D. Crystal "in the fundamental value of multilingualism as a necessary means of communication on a global scale" [2, p. 21]. But we believe that languages are not only means of communication, but also "a means of penetrating into the mental space of a foreign culture" [7, p. 107]. If languages were just simple channels for transmitting information under different sound design, then they could easily replace each other, and their reduction to one language would be a good result for humanity. To ensure good communication between people, one language is really enough. But language is not only a neutral tool for the communication of ideas,

language takes part in the production of thought. To a certain extent, every time we perceive and think about this or that event, we have the opportunity to transform it in language. It is very difficult to imagine the transmission of human thought in the situation of a single language, since the needs of human thinking and perception always exceed the possibilities of expressing one particular language. Therefore, it is necessary to support the diversity of languages, the diversity of cultures. There are no languages, on the one hand, and cultures, on the other, but there are languages-cultures [12]. Language is "the contribution of every nation to the common treasury of mankind." Lost languages can never be revived from non-existence. Their conservation is as important as the preservation of the environment and endangered species. Awareness of the importance of this issue has led to the creation of many international organizations whose mission is to record and preserve for posterity the largest number of endangered languages [2].

We believe that one of the ways to preserve the cultural diversity of the world is tourism, so it is necessary to improve intercultural communication in this area. To this end, it is necessary to strengthen the role of foreign languages and foreign language communicative competence in the curricula of tourism universities as a significant component of a graduate's complex of multicultural competencies.

This strengthening must be carried out both quantitatively and qualitatively:

- Firstly, teaching foreign languages should be carried out on the basis of a multilingual approach. In the explanatory dictionary of social science terms N.E. Yatsenko (1999), multilingualism is interpreted as "multilingualism, the use of several languages within a certain social community (primarily the state); the use by an individual (group of people) of several languages, each of which is chosen in accordance with a specific communicative situation". Since the tourism business is a social community that is characterized by specific communication situations with representatives of different countries and cultures, we believe that a multilingual approach in professional tourism education should be to provide students with the opportunity to study several foreign languages at the university at the same time, which will be useful in their future professional activities. Students need to be provided with the means of various language systems, with different levels of their mastery;

- secondly, you need to understand that for people of tourism specialties, knowing the language as a means of elementary communication is not enough. They need "a living language that lives in the world of its speakers", and "studying it without knowing this world ... deprives a tourist industry employee of the opportunity to use this language as a means of communication" [2, p. 127]. In our opinion, today in tourism education it is especially important to implement the relationship between language and culture, to emphasize it, to explain to students that to speak a foreign

language means to be familiar with the culture of another people, to be able to feel it, to understand the cultural characteristics of representatives of different regions and countries, their motives. behavior. This is what ensures the possibility of successful international and intercultural interaction and communication.

It is proved that thanks to foreign languages, intelligence develops, cultural isolation is overcome, value-semantic guidelines are established, which is why we believe that on their basis a university graduate will be able to self-realize in the modern multicultural space of tourism as a subject of culture, a cultural referent.

Among the pedagogical possibilities of a foreign language in the formation of students' multicultural competence L.Yu. Danilova identifies a number of significant components:

- meaningful (the process of obtaining knowledge about the native country and the country of the language being studied contributes to the formation of students' own beliefs, their speech and language culture, provides a positive attitude towards a foreign language not only as an opportunity to communicate with representatives of other countries and understand each other, but also as a way to the way of developing multicultural competencies);

- activity (learning a language as an activity in general, as well as specific actions of students to develop the skills and abilities to use a foreign language in various types of speech activity contribute to the assertion of an active life position of students, respect for the work of other people, the adoption of norms of cultural activity);

- communicative ("interaction in which students act as participants in the process of perception and production of foreign language information in a certain situation, with a specific goal towards a certain partner" contributes to the assimilation of cultural and ethical norms of behavior, strengthening interpersonal relationships, acquiring social experience, developing responsiveness, etc.);

- motivational-value (work on the language forms a value attitude towards the future profession and a conscious positive motivation for the chosen specialty, stimulates the desire for self-realization, develops a value attitude towards knowledge in general, the desire to engage in self-education);

- intercultural (inclusion of students in intercultural communication with native speakers provides a phased implementation of the "dialogue of cultures", which contributes to a better understanding of "foreign" and native cultures);

- emotional (creating a favorable psychological atmosphere in the classroom of a foreign language helps to reveal the various positive aspects of the student's personality, develop the ability to reflect).

Thus, the researcher comes to the conclusion that a foreign language is one of the main means of developing the multicultural competence of an individual, its pedagogical capabilities are significant [1, p. 58–65].

According to E.N. Tkachuk, it is possible not only to develop the multicultural competence of students, but also to implement the idea of harmonious interaction of diverse cultures, where each is "a valuable catalyst for students to master the world culture and in-depth understanding of their own" [6, p. 109].

One cannot but agree with scientists (E.I. Passov, T.N. Tkachuk, S.G. Ter-Minasova, E.M. Vereshchagin, V.G. Kostomarov, E. Phipps, G. Jack, etc.), who consider foreign language culture to be the variety of spiritual and material cultural values that belongs to different peoples and is learned by students in the process of learning a foreign language. In this process, a dialogue of cultures takes place, because, entering a new foreign language space, students act as translators of their own culture, they compare and contrast them.

University graduates will literally have to carry out a dialogue of cultures (and sometimes a polylogue), as they will interact with consumers of tourism services that differ in different cultural characteristics. "Tourism, especially international tourism, is a dialogue of cultures, and for the dialogue to take place, knowledge of the language of the partner is necessary" [17]. It is well known that this knowledge can ensure the success of not only an individual employee, but the entire organization as a whole [11, p. 37]. Professional knowledge of two or more foreign languages together with traditional tourism education will allow graduates to be competitive not only in multinational, multicultural Uzbekistan, but also beyond its borders.

Foreign languages for an employee of the tourism industry (namely, languages, and not just one language) are an important "trump card in the sleeve", the main professional tool, a means of interethnic communication, intellectual and social interaction. Tourism is a multicultural environment, and in the era of globalization and informatization, knowledge of foreign languages for people working in tourism is not a luxury, but a realized necessity, an opportunity to understand well the features of the world's diversity.

From the point of view of management, the essence of the multicultural approach is that "any organization that wants to be successful must use a hierarchy of languages to describe its activities. Moreover, the language of the lower level is the language of production operations, the language of the upper level is the language in which the mission, strategy and values of the organization are formulated. In accordance with this principle, activities described in the language of one level or another should be evaluated in the language of a higher level. At the same time, any representative of the team must understand the hierarchy of languages, know how his activity correlates with

the implementation of the mission of the organization. The presence of such a hierarchy gives a common guideline for creativity to each member of the team. Its absence leads to the loss of common guidelines, resulting in the growth of communication barriers, aggravation of contradictions between departments, a decrease in the ability to innovate, and loss of efficiency" [10].

So, based on a multicultural approach in management, we believe that in the process of studying at a university, a student should master several languages at different levels:

1. The native language, the level of knowledge of which should be quite high, here special attention must be paid to the culture of speech. "Native language is a system that a person learns from infancy in parallel with the development of consciousness. Therefore, the mental and linguistic systems and the cultural attitudes associated with them are perceived by man and ethnic group as the only correct ones" [17]. And although this circumstance sometimes creates significant barriers in interethnic, intercultural dialogue, the study of foreign languages takes place on the basis of the native language by comparing and analyzing language systems and phenomena. And since mental activity is reflected adequately and more fully in the native language, the mission, strategy and values of the organization are formulated in it.

2. Foreign languages (one or two or more), which a professional needs to know and actively use, or, as they say: "to know perfectly", because these are the main means of providing foreign language communication and multicultural interaction.

What does it mean to "know perfectly"? And are there limits to "perfection"?

According to one of the fundamental concepts of excellence, this definition is interpreted as the achievement of results that satisfy all interested parties. The encyclopedia of linguistics cites the terms that exist in the English language: "acquisition" - "acquisition" (this is the "grasping" of the language, its natural assimilation) and "learning" - "conscious study", as well as "knowledge" - "knowledge of the language" and "proficiency" - "proficiency in the language". Knowing a language does not mean simply mastering linguistic and cultural information. Here it is important to be able to actively use your knowledge of the language to solve all the necessary tasks in a variety of communication situations. "Knowing a foreign language perfectly is such a degree of language proficiency when a person switches from his native language to a foreign one without tension, and native speakers of this language will not even suspect from his speech that he is a foreigner" [10]. Perfect knowledge of a foreign language for a specialist in the tourism sector, in our opinion, is a necessary knowledge of a foreign language to the extent and form of perfection to which it satisfies all interested parties for effective business. And this does not mean at all that

you need to speak a foreign language like your native language. You need to have such communicative competence that will allow you to easily understand foreign speech (receptive types of speech activity: reading, listening) within the necessary limits and switch from your native language to a foreign language (productive types of speech activity: speaking, writing) to achieve your goals.

3. "Languages of production operations" - these are some other foreign languages, knowledge of which will be sufficient at a receptive level that does not involve speech creativity. A specialist can understand foreign speech in one language by ear, but at the same time not have the skills of spontaneous oral speech, he may not perceive another foreign language by ear, but he will easily understand the information if it is presented in the form of a text.

So, we believe that modern students, along with their native language, need to study a number of foreign languages, two of which are included in the basic (mandatory) part, and the others in the variable (profile) part of the humanitarian, socio-economic cycle of the main educational program for the preparation of a bachelor . We believe that the study of English should be mandatory, since it has real opportunities to obtain the status of the main world language (the so-called lingua franca). This is the language of international communication, which is developing in three directions (native, official and foreign) and has a high rate of spread in the world (almost a quarter of the world's population already knows it to a sufficient extent) [3, p. 21].

The second compulsory foreign language can be French, Spanish, German, Chinese, Arabic, Korean i.e. the language of the main tourist destinations and flows from and to our country. As an optional part, students should be offered to study various other languages at will, which may be useful for students for future functioning in the conditions of international cooperation in specific regions. It is necessary to draw students' attention to the fact that if someone wants to make a career in a particular country or region, he needs to master the language of the region or direction he has chosen as early as possible and with better quality. It should be noted that the study of this group of languages should be carried out as part of optional classes and additional professional education.

A student who studies the first foreign language (then the second and beyond) and its culture (the second culture and beyond) does not lose the linguistic competence that he had in his language and culture. And the new competence in the acquisition process is not completely independent of the previous one. The student does not acquire two foreign language ways to act and communicate. He becomes bilingual (multilingual) and learns to be multicultural. Linguistic and cultural competencies relating to each language are modified through knowledge of the "foreign" and require

awareness. As cognitive components, they are part of the complex of multicultural competencies acquired at the university and contribute to the development of a rich and complex personality, the acquisition of the ability to learn other languages and open oneself to new cultural experiences.

Thus, through the simultaneous knowledge of languages and cultures, students form and develop multicultural competencies, which consist in the ability to act adequately in different social systems of norms within the same society, as well as in different societies. People who have developed such competencies are able to better capture cultural differences, tolerantly, respectfully treat the diversity of world values, while maintaining their own identity, and, therefore, can live and work effectively in a multicultural society. It is obvious that for graduates of different directions, as future participants in intercultural dialogue, quantitative and qualitative knowledge of foreign languages and cultures will facilitate integration in a multicultural world and cooperation in the modern labour market.

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